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EQUALITY, DIVERSITY AND INCLUSION BEST PRACTICES

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TABLE OF CONTENTS

Aalto University: Shaking Up Tech	1
Budapest University of Technology and Economics: Equal Opportunities Counselling Service	2
ETH Zurich: Campaign: Respect. Full stop.	3
Karlsruhe Institute of Technology: Development Program for High-Potentials.....	4
KTH Royal Institute of Technology: Gender and Leadership for Change (GOFL)	5
Norwegian University of Science and Technology	6
<i>Politecnico di Torino</i> : Survey Evaluation, Monitoring and Support Quality of Life	7
<i>Politecnico di Torino</i> : POLIFAMILY (POLICINO+AGEING)	8
Poznan University of Technology: PUT around the world – Intercultural <i>Café</i>	9
RWTH Aachen University: Diversity Days (<i>Tage der Vielfalt</i>)	10
RWTH Aachen University: forumDIVERSITY	11
University of Strathclyde: Equally Safe in Higher Education (ESHE)	12
University of Strathclyde: Family Friendly Research Leave	13
<i>Technische Universität Berlin</i> : Joint Programmes	14
<i>Technische Universität Braunschweig</i> : Baby Bag	15
<i>Technische Universität Braunschweig</i> : PROfessorin	16
<i>Technische Universität Wien</i> : Men and women at TU Wien: figures, facts, analyses	17
<i>Technische Universität Wien</i> : Target agreements with deans/faculties	18
University College Dublin: Equality Impact Assessment Tool	19
University College Dublin: Gender Identity and Expression	21
Ghent University: Coaching and Diversity	23
Ghent University: HeForShe@UGent.....	24
<i>Universidad Politécnica de Madrid</i> : Equality Unit	25

AALTO UNIVERSITY: SHAKING UP TECH

PROJECT TITLE	Shaking up Tech
RESPONSIBLE	Aalto University
CONTACT PERSON	Marja Niemi
PHONE NUMBER	+358504302084
E-MAIL ADDRESS	marja.niemi@aalto.fi
TIME FRAME	2018-
FUNDING	mainly internal + some funding from partner companies
BUDGET (IN €)	€ 55,000 annually
TARGET GROUP	young women studying advanced mathematics in high school
WEBPAGE	https://shakinguptech.com/

200 young women from various high schools in Finland took part in the first Shaking up Tech event at Aalto University on the International Day of the Girl 11 October. The goal of the event was to inspire and encourage talented young women to apply for studies in technology. With the event, Aalto University and partner companies wanted to shake the image that young people have of the field of technology, and show a glimpse of the many ways they can make a positive impact on the world by choosing a career in technology. The morning's talks from tech influencers outlined the various and exciting education and career opportunities in the field of technology. The event was continued with 18 parallel hands-on workshops where e.g. some of the participants got to combine mathematics and art, some had their first try at coding and some had a chance to produce a new kind of cellulose-based textile fibre from recycled materials. Finally the event ended with a study fair where students got to know Aalto University's study opportunities and student life, and also met the event's partner companies. The event was inspired by the Teknologicamp of NTNU and it will be organized annually. Shaking up Tech received excellent feedback from the participants and enhanced their interest in the fields of technology (see Figure below). Furthermore, 97% of the 150 participants who answered the feedback survey of the event were likely to tell about the event at their schools, increasing the impact of the event further to other young people.

BUDAPEST UNIVERSITY OF TECHNOLOGY AND ECONOMICS: EQUAL OPPORTUNITIES COUNSELLING SERVICE

PROJECT TITLE	Equal Opportunities Counselling Service
RESPONSIBLE	Budapest University of Technology and Economics
CONTACT PERSON	Zita DEMJÉN
PHONE NUMBER	+3614633983
E-MAIL ADDRESS	eselyegyenloseg@hszi.bme.hu
FUNDING	internal
TARGET GROUP	mainly students from university with special needs
WEBPAGE	https://hszi.bme.hu/en/Counselling/equal-opportunities/

Internal and external professionals come to the university for this day and give presentation and give consultancy for the interested students.

Equal Opportunities Counselling Service

While you are a university student, as a person with special needs, you are eligible to receive several services to support your studies and to achieve success on the labour-market in the future.

[Information about special needs](#)

A student (applicant) is considered disabled if he/she is challenged with one or some of the followings: physical, sensory or speech impairments, multiple disabilities (in case of simultaneous occurrence), autism spectrum condition or any other specific learning disabilities (severe learning, attention deficit and behavioural disorders). The university endeavours to support students with long term medical conditions.

Registration

In order to receive the services, register as soon as possible! You can request to be registered any time while you are a university student.

[How to register?](#)

Make an appointment with the equal opportunity coordinator at one of her contact details. We will ask you to show us the medical report stating the type and level of your disabilities and the original copy of your medical report; therefore please bring them with you to the pre-arranged counselling session. You will also need to fill in the equal opportunities form which you may download from [here](#).

Equal Opportunity Services

After registration you may use our services listed below. None of these are mandatory. In case you would like to apply for either of them, you need to make a request.

[Our services for registered students](#)

- personal assistance (note-taking/tutor service)
- modified learning conditions
- individual equal opportunity counselling
- get information about disabled transportation options, request parking card to use it in the university area and make proposals in relation to barrier-free options
- peer mentoring
- transition support

You might think that you do not need these options right now. In case you change your mind later, we encourage you to apply as soon as possible so we can provide the most suitable solutions for you.

ETH ZURICH: CAMPAIGN: RESPECT. FULL STOP.

PROJECT TITLE	“Respect. Full stop.”
RESPONSIBLE	ETH Zurich
CONTACT PERSON	Renate Schubert, Associate Vice-President for Equal Opportunities
PHONE NUMBER	+4144632 62 76
E-MAIL ADDRESS	equal@sl.ethz.ch
TIME FRAME	September 2017 – May 2018 (main campaign); smaller activities in Fall 2018; Code of Conduct unlimited
FUNDING	Internal
TARGET GROUP	Faculty, staff and students at ETH Zurich
WEBPAGE	www.respect.ethz.ch (English), www.respekt.ethz.ch (German)

Since 2004, ETH Zurich has run a series of “RESPECT” campaigns to raise general awareness about inappropriate behaviour and remind everyone of commonly accepted principles. In the 2017/18 academic year, ETH Zurich ran a new campaign based around the slogan “Respect. Full stop.” (in German: “Mach einen Punkt. Aus Respekt.”) The campaign aimed to encourage all ETH members to respect and never overstep personal boundaries of others. In a first phase in the Autumn Semester 2017, the campaign sought to raise awareness about the topic among ETH members using posters with attention-grabbing phrases related to the slogan “Respect. Full stop.” A short colourful video clip was displayed in many public spaces of ETH, reinforcing the messages of the posters. Their intention was to encourage people to reflect on personal boundaries and inappropriate types of behaviour as well as to stimulate discussions about what “respect” means. A special webpage was published, providing information about how to act respectfully. This website has also listed all ETH units that can be contacted for support in cases of discrimination, bullying, violence or sexual harassment. In the following Spring Semester 2018, the “Code of Conduct - Respect” was introduced to all ETH members. The respective brochure was accompanied by a new series of posters, displaying conflicting word pairs to highlight which types of behaviour are seen as acceptable or unacceptable at ETH Zurich. In addition, a second video clip was produced to convey the key idea of the RESPECT Campaign. In Fall 2018, all new ETH students received a small gift that drew their attention to the website of the RESPECT Campaign. All campaign material was produced in German and English. The respective posters were visible all across the institution and articles were launched in staff and student media. Furthermore, a competition to invent additional conflicting word pairs was organized.

Has ETH Zurich’s RESPECT Campaign been a success so far? The answer depends on the measurement criteria used. Yes, it has been a great success since the provocative posters induced a lot of discussions among ETH members on all levels. ETH citizens discussed whether specific types of behavior should be classified as respectful or not, and whether they know or are convinced that certain types of disrespectful behavior can or cannot be observed at ETH. The campaign stirred emotions and made it clear for many ETH members that neither the university as a whole nor individual members can turn a blind eye in cases of disrespect. In this sense, the awareness for the topic “respect” was raised in a broad and “natural” way – hopefully leading to less disrespectful behavior than before the campaign. In pure numbers, no success seems to be measurable so far. ETH does not observe a decrease in the number of cases of disrespectful behavior in the aftermath of its most recent RESPECT campaign – on the contrary. Yet, this could be seen as a good sign since more university members are identifying disrespectful behavior and bring it to the table. Hence, chances to identify hotspots and find adequate solutions seem to increase. The expectation would be that this helps making the atmosphere at ETH more open and respectful – and hence making it a better place for working and studying and for excellent science and teaching in a broad sense. Therefore, ETH Zurich encourages other universities to start an endeavor like the RESPECT campaign. It will pay off in the long run!

KARLSRUHE INSTITUTE OF TECHNOLOGY: DEVELOPMENT PROGRAM FOR HIGH-POTENTIALS

PROJECT TITLE	Development Program for High-Potentials
RESPONSIBLE	Karlsruhe Institute of Technology
CONTACT PERSON	Yulia Kokott
PHONE NUMBER	+497260846531
E-MAIL ADDRESS	yulia.kokott@kit.edu
TIME FRAME	Duration of the program: approx. 1 year
FUNDING	External funding – the program was developed as a gender equality measure of a CRC → gender equality budget of the CRC
BUDGET (IN €)	Budget depends on the number of participants and measures agreed in the Individual Development Plans
TARGET GROUP	Postdoctoral researchers
WEBPAGE	http://www.sfb1176.kit.edu/563.php

The CRC – together with the service unit *Human Resource Development* – developed and implemented the Development Program for High Potentials in Chemistry. Next to the development of postdoctoral researchers, the primary objective of the program was to support especially female researchers to assume positions as Principal Investigators (PI) in an anticipated second funding period. Eleven postdoctoral researchers (therefrom eight women) from the CRC were encouraged to participate in this exclusive and highly individualised program. Out of eleven postdoctoral researchers that were qualified and thus selected for this program, eight were women, therefore meeting the goal of increasing the relative female presence.

To support the Development Program, the intensive involvement of current PIs as well as a mentoring relationship with experienced (internal or external) mentors was considered very important. After the completion of the first part of the program (Evaluation of personal and professional situation, so-called “*Standortbestimmung*”), the Executive Board decided on the potential female candidates for the role of PI during the next funding period of the CRC. These candidates were offered additional measures in order to prepare for the role of a PI.

All other program participants were supported with the specified measures defined in the Individual Development Plans.

The following results and impact were achieved:

- Increasing of gender awareness among PIs and CRC members
- Program participants took over leading positions in academia or industry
- Additional financial support from the CRC for identified candidates
- Personal development of program participants, reflection about their career aims

KTH ROYAL INSTITUTE OF TECHNOLOGY: GENDER AND LEADERSHIP FOR CHANGE (GOFL)

PROJECT TITLE	Gender and Leadership for Change (GOFL)
RESPONSIBLE	KTH's Vice President for Gender Equality and Values
CONTACT PERSON	Professor Anna Wahl, Associate Professor Charlotte Holgersson
PHONE NUMBER	+4687906759
E-MAIL ADDRESS	anna.wahl@indek.kth.se
TIME FRAME	One year (autumn 2017-autumn 2018)
FUNDING	Internal funding only, through allocated funds for gender mainstreaming
BUDGET (IN €)	€ 10,000 (estimated)
TARGET GROUP	Women in top academic and administrative positions within the KTH organisation, as well as the KTH institution at large.

GOFL is a development program that was executed 2017-2018, which involved eighteen women in leading positions at KTH within faculty and administration alike. The aim of GOFL was to transform and empower women into becoming leaders for change - thereby increasing women's involvement and influence in the building and design of KTH's long-term work for gender equality. The year-long program consisted of monthly meet-ups, focusing on constructive and practical change leadership in the participants own work environment. The meet-ups, which were led by KTH's Vice President for Gender Equality and Values and her team, contained lectures by invited guests in the field of gender equality etc., discussions, reflections, practical group exercises and theoretical studies, as well as individual homework to be done between meetings. The year both began and ended with a two-day conference in order to kick-off and sum-up, respectively, the work that was done.

Evaluation will take place under the start of 2019 as part of KTH Equality Office's yearly documentation. Already, it is evident that GOFL has clearly had an impact consisting of increased awareness and recognition regarding equality issues overall within the units and departments where the GOFL's are working, when it comes to both cultural and structural aspects of inequality. Several of the GOFL women have initiated processes within their local work environments/research groups/administrative units that benefit KTH:s overall work with gender equality –these initiatives are part of the central processes of sustaining a high quality of education and research, of competence provision, of career planning and evaluation throughout all of KTH. As well, we can see a strong sense of unity and support among the GOFL members, which enable and strengthen them in their daily work for equality. There might be more GOFL-programs starting in the future, giving both women and men the possibility to become KTH's leaders for change.

NORWEGIAN UNIVERSITY OF SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY

PROJECT TITLE	"Gender balance from below" – an innovative approach at NTNU
RESPONSIBLE	"BALANSE" – a program by the Norwegian Research Council Goal: enhancing gender balance in top positions and research leadership
CONTACT PERSON	Professor Vivian Anette Lagesen
PHONE NUMBER	+47 91172760
E-MAIL ADDRESS	Vivian.lagesen@ntnu.no
TIME FRAME	2015 - 2018
FUNDING	NTNU Internal NOK 4 mill. Norwegian Research Council NOK 4 mill.
BUDGET (IN €)	€ 823,944
TARGET GROUP	Change through processes of learning, based in analysis of the situation on Department level
WEBPAGE	https://www.ntnu.edu/genderbalance

Large variations in the proportion of women on the level of departments (larger than between faculties) indicate that gender balance problems are local. Previous efforts have mainly been provision of incentives and measures from above. They have had some, but not much effect. Previous efforts have aimed at strengthening individual women's opportunities. We want to focus on:

- The local environment - Management in academia
- The understanding of the gender (in) balance -Inclusion work
- We need to work from an inclusion thinking, rather than exclusion thinking
- Efforts that will contribute to a positive process of learning for the organization.

What is it that works? Which departments succeeds in getting women in top positions and why? What may we learn from these departments? Look for new and different kind of solutions om how concrete efforts may be designed and adapted to local contexts. In other words: The basis for change is produced through acknowledgement and learning, and in that way the culture may change as well. A process-based approach.

Action research: based on actions, using experience, and learning as a foundation for creating change.

Participative research: Three workshops with representatives from twelve departments. Three sub-projects:

1. Preparing phase/mapping/research
2. Workshop-series
3. Evaluation research

The following results and impact were achieved:

- The most important measure has been the action research project.
- The importance of anchoring gender balance work in management and also in the lower levels of the organization
- Seeking knowledge and mapping the situation for analysing the need for measures has led to increased knowledge and increased engagement.
- Driving forces to nudge, discipline and contribute with expertise (project team) has been crucial.
- Allocation of resources were important – both practically and symbolically
- 'Hawthorne'-effect, increased attention and visibility of such work should not be underestimated
- Increased knowledge and awareness has also induced a change in perspective among department heads

POLITECNICO DI TORINO: SURVEY EVALUATION, MONITORING AND SUPPORT QUALITY OF LIFE

PROJECT TITLE	On-line Survey "Evaluation, Monitoring and Support Quality of Life in the Organization"
RESPONSIBLE	Politecnico di Torino
CONTACT PERSON	Cristina Coscia
PHONE NUMBER	+39110906407
E-MAIL ADDRESS	cristina.coscia@polito.it
TIME FRAME	Start in 2017 - unlimited
FUNDING	Internal Funding/Politecnico di Torino Budget
BUDGET (IN €)	Budget 2017: € 18,250 budget 2018: € 26,000
TARGET GROUP	Academic and administrative staff, Research Fellows and students (students in 2019)
WEBPAGE	Survey 2017: https://www.swas.polito.it/services/cug/doc_cug.asp

In June 2017, on the initiative of its Equal Opportunities Committee (CUG), Politecnico di Torino launched the "Survey on the quality of organizational life" with the scientific contribution of the Department of Psychology of the Università degli Studi di Torino.

The survey was addressed to all the academic and technical-administrative staff. The aim of the survey was to collect the opinions of those who work at the university regarding a list of indicators able to define the quality of organizational life, highlighting elements that can affect positively or negatively the well-being of the Politecnico di Torino professors and Staff.

DATA

The Survey 2017 had a good success: respondents were 79.50% of the total Administrative Staff; 46.65% of the Professors; 38.50% of the Research Fellows.

RESULTS

The final report presents a "health assessment" in which the main areas of well-being and stress are highlighted for each kind of PoliTo population (Administrative Staff, Professors, Research Fellows), in relation to three key factors: work factors, organizational factors and interpersonal/relational factors

IMPACT AND FUTURE DEVELOPMENT

The Politecnico di Torino governance has considered Survey results a precious tool to support the identification and implementation of new actions aimed at the enhancement of the well-being and quality of life at Politecnico di Torino (PoliTo Strategic Plan 2018-2024). For this reason, the Survey will be proposed every 2 years and in 2019 it will be proposed also to students.

POLITECNICO DI TORINO: POLIFAMILY (POLICINO+AGEING)

PROJECT TITLE	POLIFAMILY (POLICINO+AGEING)
RESPONSIBLE	Politecnico di Torino
CONTACT PERSON	Cristina Coscia
PHONE NUMBER	+39110906407
E-MAIL ADDRESS	cristina.coscia@polito.it
TIME FRAME	Policino was created in 2005 as "babyparking"; in 2006 it was incorporated into a larger project called "Polifamily" which contains several care services: nursery school / babyparking (<i>Policino</i>); elderly care; baby siter at home
FUNDING	ESF from 2005 to 2006. From 2007 internal funds/Politecnico di Torino budget
BUDGET (IN €)	1. POLICINO (Budget 2017 = 150.000€; Budget 2018 = 165.000€) 2. BABY-SITTING SERVICE AT HOME (49,000€, 5% VAT excluded) 3. ELDERLY ASSISTANCE (49,000€, 5% VAT excluded)
TARGET GROUP	Academic and administrative staff, Research Fellows and students (students can benefit only of POLICINO)
WEBPAGE (AVAILABLE ONLY IN ITALIAN)	https://www.swas.polito.it/services/cug/vita_lavoro.asp https://www.swas.polito.it/services/cug/micronido.asp https://www.swas.polito.it/services/cug/babyparking.asp https://www.swas.polito.it/services/cug/assist_domicil.asp

POLICINO

In April 2005 the "Policino" *baby parking* was created to give a flexible response to the high percentage of female workers with different working time. The service is open to the children of all University members (students, professors, researchers, technical-administrative staff and collaborators) and has up to 24 places for children from 13 months to 6 years. The *baby parking* offers care -on reservation- for a flexible amount of time within the opening hours (from 8:00 to 19:00). The University funds the majority of the costs and the families contribute to the financing. Starting from September 2013, in addition to the *baby parking* service, a small day nursery was created to better meet the needs of staff and students. "Policino" continues to be the name of the new 'reinforced' service. The day nursery has up to 20 places for children from 12 to 36 months and is open from 8:30 am to 4:30 pm. From 4:30 pm to 7:00 pm, a baby parking service is available on reservation.

BABY-SITTING SERVICE AT HOME

The service is open to children from 0 to 13 months of all University members (students, professors, researchers, technical-administrative staff and collaborators)

ELDERLY ASSISTANCE

The service supports a work/life balance for the staff of the Politecnico di Torino who is facing difficult situations due to the needs of elderly or disabled family members. The service can also be provided for the benefit of the staff of Politecnico who are temporarily not self-sufficient or going through serious health problems. The following three types of services are available:

1. Home care services provided continuously by specialized care givers, holding the professional qualification issued by accredited professional agencies (e.g. support for personal hygiene and meal preparation, cleaning the house, keeping company, reservation of medical visits)
2. Home care services for disabled family members provided continuously by specialized care givers (e.g. support for the educational tasks of the family and for the relief to the family; maintenance and / or strengthening of the psycho-physical abilities of the disabled; relational support)
3. Occasional services provided by professional care givers

The duration of the service can be between a minimum of two and a maximum of 15 hours per week, with a minimum of 2 hours per day.

In 2017 and in 2018 all available places have been used. Its users assessed the service as excellent and in 2017/2018, there was an increase, thanks to a more effective communication and promotion of the service.

Università degli Studi di Torino intends to start a similar service based on the *Politecnico di Torino* good practice

POZNAN UNIVERSITY OF TECHNOLOGY: PUT AROUND THE WORLD – INTERCULTURAL CAFÉ

PROJECT TITLE	PUT around the world – Intercultural Café
RESPONSIBLE	Poznan University of Technology
CONTACT PERSON	Emilia Wojtczak
PHONE NUMBER	+48616653544
E-MAIL ADDRESS	emilia.wojtczak@put.poznan.pl
TIME FRAME	March 2017- December 2019
FUNDING	From March 2017 – October 2018 – internal Since November 2018 external - the programme is co-financed from the European Social Fund under the Operational Programme Knowledge, Education, Development, a non-competitive project entitled Increasing competencies of the academic staff and the institutions' potential to receive people from abroad – Welcome to Poland implemented under the Measure defined in application for co-financing of the project No POWR.03.03.00-00-PN14/18
BUDGET (IN €)	€ 250/month – € 450/month
TARGET GROUP	Polish and international students, employees of the PUT
WEBPAGE	http://www.put.poznan.pl

The Intercultural Café is an initiative proposed by the LLL and International Education Office of Poznan University of Technology. The Intercultural Café aimed at integrating the academic community, cultural exchange, enlargement awareness about Poland among foreign students and awareness about the countries of origin of foreign students from the Poznan University of Technology among Polish students.

Meetings are organized every month, students give presentations about different topics like: cuisine, music, wedding traditions, national games, hobbies, beautiful places in the country presented, the influence of globalization in their cultures. There is time for discussion with a cup of coffee. There are two special editions for Christmas and Easter with presentations about celebrations of those holidays around the world, students do decorations and taste traditional food. Meetings are dedicated for both, Polish and international students of Poznan University of Technology and universities in Poznan, as well as employees of the Poznan University of Technology.

Studying abroad can be a life-changing experience because it exposes people to completely new and different worlds, mind-sets, values, attitudes, and perceptions. Being immersed in a different culture can be challenging therefore PUT is trying to contribute to making this transition into a new reality as smooth as possible. Members of the PUT community have a chance to meet in an informal pleasant environment and be engaged in cultural exchange. It is a platform to give students the opportunity to learn more about Poland, present their home countries and learn about the countries of their international friends from PUT. It is also the opportunity to develop personal skills by giving a presentation in front of the audience. Finally, it is a place to meet friends and spend time together. The meeting enjoys great interest and receiving good feedback from participants. Students are active; they send proposals to be a speaker and one of the international students moderates the meeting. More and more employees are interested in the Intercultural Café and attend some of the meetings sharing their own intercultural experience.

RWTH AACHEN UNIVERSITY: DIVERSITY DAYS (TAGE DER VIELFALT)

PROJECT TITLE	Diversity Days ("Tage der Vielfalt")
RESPONSIBLE	RWTH Aachen University Rectorate Staff Unit Integration Team – Human Resources, Gender and Diversity Management (IGaD), RWTH Aachen University
CONTACT PERSON	Katrin Feldmann
PHONE NUMBER	+492418090627
E-MAIL ADDRESS	genderanddiversity@rwth-aachen.de
TIME FRAME (START-/END DATE; LIMITED/UNLIMITED)	Biannually since 2016
FUNDING (INTERNAL/EXTERNAL; WHO IS FUNDING)	Internal
TARGET GROUP	All university members
WEBPAGE	http://www.igad.rwth-aachen.de/cms/IGAD/Diversity-Management/~qwig/Tage-der-Vielfalt/?lidx=1

The Diversity Days are a biannual collaboration project of different university players in diversity management, in particular of the forumDIVERSITY. It started in 2016 with the aim to raise awareness on diversity issues.

In 2016, the Diversity Days provided a wide range of offers with respect to all diversity dimensions. A big opening event provided an opportunity for student's initiatives and representations of different target groups to present their activities and illustrated the cultural diversity at RWTH in the shape of a marketplace.

In 2018, the focus was on disability and chronic illness. This time the objective was to emphasise the importance and potential of students and employees with impairments. A large number of events, workshops and films were organised in line with the slogan "Inclusion makes us stronger" (In German: "Inklusion macht stark").

The event was evaluated by means of an evaluation form. Results showed a varying participation rate by group of university affiliates and a high satisfaction rate of the participants. The plan is to further integrate the Diversity Days into the event calendar of the University as well as to grant leaves of absence for employees and students who wish to participate in the event.

RWTH AACHEN UNIVERSITY: FORUMDIVERSITY

PROJECT TITLE	forumDIVERSITY – Central Advisory Board for shaping the Diversity Policy of RWTH Aachen University
RESPONSIBLE	Rectorate staff unit Integration Team – Human Resources, Gender and Diversity Management (IGaD)
CONTACT PERSON	Head of IGaD
PHONE NUMBER	+492418090627
E-MAIL ADDRESS	genderanddiversity@igad.rwth-aachen.de
TIME FRAME	Since 2015
FUNDING	Internal
TARGET GROUP	All university members
WEBPAGE	http://www.igad.rwth-aachen.de/cms/IGAD/Diversity-Management/~pvge/forumDIVERSITY/lidx/1/

The forumDIVERSITY has been established as a central advisory board for shaping the Diversity Policy at RWTH Aachen University. It is hosted by the rectorate staff unit for gender and diversity management. The aim is to inform and reflect about the development of an open and inclusive university. Therefore, forumDIVERSITY focuses on opening the university (educational equality, equitable access and broader social participation), initiating cultural change (appreciation of diversity, equal study and career paths), designing a life-phase-oriented staff policy (consideration of diverse life plans as well as inclusion of individual qualification phases) and strengthening of gender and diversity skills (diversity-sensitive leadership and non-discriminatory interaction) in line with the university's strategic objectives.

Members of the forumDIVERSITY are among others the Vice-Rector for Human Resources Management and Development, Equal Opportunities Officer, Representative Council for staff with disabilities, In-house Social Counselling, Operational Health Management, General Students' Committee (AStA), representative of students with disability or chronic illness and some representatives of the administration of the university.

The forumDIVERSITY meets twice a year. One major common project are the Diversity Days realized in 2016 and 2018 up until now.

UNIVERSITY OF STRATHCLYDE: EQUALLY SAFE IN HIGHER EDUCATION (ESHE)

PROJECT TITLE	Equally Safe in Higher Education (ESHE)
RESPONSIBLE	University of Strathclyde
CONTACT PERSON	Anni Donaldson
PHONE NUMBER	+44 141 4448602
E-MAIL ADDRESS	anni.donaldson@strath.ac.uk
TIME FRAME	Initial research project 2016-2018
FUNDING	Initial research project funded by Scottish Government
BUDGET (IN €)	Approximately €907,419 (£795,815)
TARGET GROUP	University students and staff
WEBPAGE	https://www.strath.ac.uk/humanities/schoolofsocialwork/socialpolicy/equallysafeinhighereducation/

Addressing themes within [Equally Safe](#), the Scottish Government's strategy for preventing and eradicating violence against women and girls, ESHE works on generating new data on attitudes to and extent of gender-based violence (GBV) within Scottish Higher Education Institutions. From 2016-2018, the project developed a toolkit, using University of Strathclyde as a pilot site, to challenge GBV across Scotland's universities. The [ESHE Toolkit](#) was developed to provide universities with an approach to preventing GBV that will create a step change in how universities approach inclusivity and equality. By acknowledging the need to address GBV at institutional level, the ESHE Toolkit aligns itself with the Scottish Government and United Nations in their recognition that GBV is both a cause and consequence of gender inequality. The Toolkit provides a practical collection of free materials and resources developed specifically for Scottish universities which can be used as they are or adapted to suit individual institutions. It includes tools on:

- GBV: Developing a whole campus response
- ESHE Research Tools
- GBV Intervention
- GBV Primary Prevention
- GBV Curriculum and Knowledge Exchange.

ESHE also develops awareness raising campaigns and GBV prevention education/training programmes for staff and students. As part of Strathclyde's implementation of the toolkit, we have produced a GBV Policy for staff, which has been accompanied by two levels of training on how to respond to GBV disclosures. The ESHE toolkit has been disseminated across the Scottish University sector. In 2018, the Scottish Funding Council issued a [Letter of Guidance](#) to all universities and colleges in Scotland requiring them to implement the ESHE Toolkit. Universities in Scotland are now expected to report on how they are adopting and implementing the Toolkit as part of their Outcome Agreements with the Scottish Funding Council and to ensure work with the ESHE Toolkit is reflected in institutional Gender Action Plans. Outcome Agreements set out what universities in Scotland are expected to deliver overall in return for public funding.

UNIVERSITY OF STRATHCLYDE: FAMILY FRIENDLY RESEARCH LEAVE

PROJECT TITLE	Family Friendly Research Leave
RESPONSIBLE	University of Strathclyde
CONTACT PERSON	Gordon Scott
PHONE NUMBER	+445482673
E-MAIL ADDRESS	gordon.scott@strath.ac.uk
TIME FRAME	2016 - present
FUNDING	Internal
TARGET GROUP	Academic staff who have returned from any period of maternity, adoption or shared parental leave of 4 calendar months or more ("Relevant Family Leave.")
WEBPAGE	https://www.strath.ac.uk/media/ps/humanresources/policies/Family_Friendly_Research_Leave_Policy.pdf . pagespeed.ce.rocfB1n-P0.pdf

The University of Strathclyde is committed to supporting parents to return from Relevant Family Leave and recognises that for Academic Staff, additional support may be required to help them balance their return with the demands of their research and to help the University to recruit and retain staff who have or may wish to take Relevant Family Leave. Under the Family Friendly Research Leave (FFRL) Policy, eligible staff are entitled to a continuous period of up to three months' paid research leave during which they have no teaching duties so that they are able to re-engage with their research duties (and knowledge exchange/citizenship where appropriate). FFRL will normally commence on the individual's return from Relevant Family Leave. Eligible staff can also access Family-Friendly (FF) mentoring support, whether or not they take FFRL. The purpose of mentoring is to: support and encourage the member of staff in their career and professional development; provide advice and suggestions about how to maximise the benefit of Keeping In Touch ("KIT") and/or Shared Parental Leave In Touch ("SPLIT") days; provide advice and suggestions about how to maximise the benefit of the teaching backfill member of staff, whilst on FFRL; where required, maintain and/or increase the confidence of the member of staff during Relevant Family Leave and/or FFRL; provide practical advice, share experiences and provide suggestions on how to balance the demands of an Academic Staff role with family life.

Around a dozen staff have taken FFRL since the policy was first introduced in 2016. The Human Resources Office has collected feedback from staff who have taken FFRL since its implementation. Responses have been extremely positive. For example, there have been cases of staff who have taken maternity leave before the introduction of FFRL and again after its introduction and who have commented on the transformational impact of the FFRL upon their second return to work.

TECHNISCHE UNIVERSITÄT BERLIN: JOINT PROGRAMMES

PROJECT TITLE	Joint Programmes
RESPONSIBLE	Technische Universität Berlin
CONTACT PERSON	Charlotte Rheinisch
PHONE NUMBER	+493031424886
E-MAIL ADDRESS	charlotte.reinisch@tu-berlin.de
TIME FRAME	Women who receive the offer of a guest professorship at the TU Berlin get a leave of absence from their companies for the duration of one or two academic semesters.
FUNDING	The project is funded through the "Professorinnenprogramm" – a program by the German government and the federal states that wishes to encourage equal opportunity structures at universities by specific actions. Per decision by the President's Office from May 2018: Two "calls for applications" will be financed with central funds (Frauenförderprogramm) until 2021. Each cycle will grant 2 guest professorships. Total budget:
BUDGET (IN €)	2 guest professorships per year, incl. a budget for equipment, student aids, travel expenses, costs incurred for selection committee meetings, and public relations. The guest professors receive a W2 salary. They may choose one of two options regarding their length of employment: - either full-time for 1 semester - or part-time (50%) for 2 semesters.
TARGET GROUP	Women professionals in the business enterprise and industrial sectors
WEBPAGE	https://www.jointpro.tu-berlin.de/menue/joint_programmes/parameter/en/

Since 2014, the TU Berlin offers a gender equality measure called „Joint Programmes for Female Scientists & Professionals“. This programme promotes alternative career paths for women in academia and inter-sectoral collaboration. Visiting professorships aim at enabling women in research & development departments of business companies to build stronger networks with academia in order to increase the percentage of women at universities in the long term. The program promotes the permeability between industry and science and recruits female role models for the TU Berlin who pass their experience on to young talented researchers.

This measure is an innovative way to recruit excellent female personnel for teaching, research and student guidance activities at the TU Berlin. Due to the excellent reputation of the TU Berlin in the area of engineering and technical sciences, the institution has a competitive edge as an employer in comparison with companies. So far, five guest professorships have been completed (including women employed at Siemens, BMW, and Volkswagen); three others will start in 2019; and for 2020, the President's Office has already decided that it will fund another two guest professorships within this framework. Known throughout Germany as a Best Practice, the TUB measure Joint Programmes was also awarded a prize in 02/2017 for its innovative character by the Stifterverband für die Wissenschaft. Many of the guest professors sponsored so far claim to find their way back into science through this support.

TECHNISCHE UNIVERSITÄT BRAUNSCHWEIG: BABY BAG

PROJECT TITLE	Baby Bag
RESPONSIBLE	Family Office of TU Braunschweig
CONTACT PERSON	Anne-Christin Eggers
PHONE NUMBER	+495313914536
E-MAIL ADDRESS	familienbuero@tu-bs.de
TIME FRAME	unlimited since september 2014
FUNDING	internal funding
TARGET GROUP	staff and students with their newborns
WEBPAGE	www.tu-braunschweig.de/chancengleichheit/familienbuero/baby-bag

The “Baby Bag” for all newborn babies of students and employees. TU Braunschweig is a consistently family-friendly university at every level. We welcome every child of students and employees with a TU Baby Bag. Our welcome bag contains a lot of useful information about offers and programs at our university as well as a little stuffed animal for the newborn children. We want to make contact with the TU parents at an early stage and get to know their experiences and wishes. That is why our president invites them to a welcome meeting twice a year and hands over the baby bags personally. This is part of the promotion of a family-friendly culture at our university.

The results concern appreciation, better communication and high acceptance.

TECHNISCHE UNIVERSITÄT BRAUNSCHWEIG: PROFESSORIN

PROJECT TITLE	PROfessorin
RESPONSIBLE	Equal Opportunities Office
CONTACT PERSON	Angela Dinghaus
PHONE NUMBER	+49 5313914547
E-MAIL ADDRESS	a.dinghaus@tu-braunschweig.de
TIME FRAME	2013 – 2019 (extension possible)
FUNDING	External: Programme for female professors II (federal and state governments promoting gender equality in science at German universities)
BUDGET (IN €)	€ 70,000 in 2018, the years before € 50,000 to € 57,000 annually
TARGET GROUP	Female professors in areas in which they are underrepresented (STEM)
WEBPAGE	https://www.tu-braunschweig.de/chancengleichheit/gleichstellung/professorin

To realise equal opportunities and gender equality women should be represented with at least 40 per cent in boards and administrative committees of the university and 50 per cent in nominations (Lower Saxony university regulations; Basic principles TU Braunschweig). This regulations can place a disproportionate burden in academic administrative autonomy in those areas in which female professors are underrepresented. To counter this affect, the TU Braunschweig developed compensation options: providing women an incentive to participate in decision-making positions. Compensatory measures are material and human resources, for instance Student assistant jobs.

Results concern regular participation of female professors - Appreciation of and discharging disproportional engagement in boards and administrative committees.

TECHNISCHE UNIVERSITÄT WIEN: MEN AND WOMEN AT TU WIEN: FIGURES, FACTS, ANALYSES

PROJECT TITLE	Men and women at TU Wien: figures, facts, analyses
RESPONSIBLE	Office for Gender Competence/TU Wien
CONTACT PERSON	Brigitte Ratzer
PHONE NUMBER	+4315880143400
E-MAIL ADDRESS	brigitte.ratzer@tuwien.ac.at
TIME FRAME	Yearly report, covering a whole calendar-year
FUNDING	No funding necessary, part of the tasks of the office
BUDGET (IN €)	No extra budget
TARGET GROUP	Rectorate, Academic Senate, report is publicly available
WEBPAGE	www.tuwien.ac.at/dle/genderkompetenz/zahlen_und_fakten/jahresberichte

Since 2012 the Office for Gender Competence compiles the report “Men and women at TU Wien: figures, facts, analyses” which comprises the following contents:

- Men/women quotas on graduation
- Overview of the progress of the women's quota
- Men/women quotas in scientific and non-scientific university staff
- Men's/women's wages
- Faculty reports and men/women quotas at the faculties
- Students

The report is presented to the rectorate as well as to the senate. It is a measure for awareness raising giving evidence to the urgency of action.

TECHNISCHE UNIVERSITÄT WIEN: TARGET AGREEMENTS WITH DEANS/FACULTIES

PROJECT TITLE	Target agreements with deans/faculties
RESPONSIBLE	Rectorate/TU Wien
CONTACT PERSON	Brigitte Ratzer
PHONE NUMBER	+4315880143400
E-MAIL ADDRESS	brigitte.ratzer@tuwien.ac.at
TIME FRAME	Every 3 years
FUNDING	No funding involved – internal agreements
TARGET GROUP	Deans/Faculties
WEBPAGE	Target agreements are not publicly available

The Rectorate concludes three-annual target agreements with each of the eight faculties. Among other things, (quantitative and qualitative) gender objectives are defined in the target agreements: the overall aim is to increase the proportion of women at all levels by effective measures. Examples for measures, which are proposed by the faculties themselves, include identifying specific vacancies or grants for which only women can apply; improving the compatibility of family and work or inviting as many women as men to congresses and workshops. Target agreements are evaluated on a yearly basis, the whole team of the rectorate is involved in this process.

By using target agreements as an instrument to define gender targets for faculties, the deans are accountable to reach predefined goals. In the past, at least some faculties have developed interesting initiatives such as women networks etc. Awareness that gender equality is an ongoing task concerning everyone (and not only the top management) is rising.

UNIVERSITY COLLEGE DUBLIN: EQUALITY IMPACT ASSESSMENT TOOL

PROJECT TITLE	Equality Impact Assessment Tool - Pilot
RESPONSIBLE	University College Dublin
CONTACT PERSON	Marcellina Fogarty
PHONE NUMBER	+35317164947
E-MAIL ADDRESS	Marcellina.fogarty@ucd.ie
TIME FRAME	February 2017 – Dec 2018
TARGET GROUP	Policy Developers
WEBPAGE	http://www.ucd.ie/equality/information/equalityimpactassessments/

UCD is committed to providing an inclusive environment for the University Community, and this is demonstrated in Strategic Objective 5 of the University Strategic Plan “Attract and retain an excellent and diverse cohort of students, faculty and staff”. In order to support this strategic objective, and to promote an inclusive and diverse work and study environment for all, an Equality Impact Assessment tool was developed as part of the University Policy Management Framework. This Policy Management Framework establishes a standard and principles for policy development, approval, implementation and review across the University, and the Equality Impact Assessment tool forms an essential element of this. The Equality Impact Assessment tool, informed by best international practice, was initially developed on a pilot basis by the UMT Equality Diversity and Inclusion Mainstreaming Sub-Group.

An Equality Impact Assessment (EIA) is a systematic and evidence-based process which verifies that the University’s policies and practices are non-discriminatory, are fair and inclusive in meeting the legitimate needs of the diverse groups that make up the University community. It is a means of looking at University policies and practices systematically from a ‘minority’ group perspective and can highlight any potential inequalities which might not be obvious to someone looking at it from a ‘majority’ group perspective. Another key component of an EIA is to identify where a policy is promoting Equality, Diversity and Inclusion in the University. The completion of this tool is mandatory, and is a requirement when seeking approval of a new or revised policy from the relevant approval body. If the EIA is not completed, the policy will not be approved.

The EIA Tool assesses University policies systematically across the ten equality grounds identified by the University: age, race, disability, socio economic status, religion, gender, sexual orientation, family status, civil status, and membership of the travelling community.

In summary the main reasons as to why it is important to undertake an EIA from a UCD perspective includes:

- They support the achievement of University Strategic Objective 5, "Attract and retain an excellent and diverse cohort of students, faculty and staff"
- They support the development of robust policies that are non-discriminatory and promote EDI in the University
- They facilitate the mainstreaming of EDI throughout the University as policy developers take responsibility for ensuring their policies are promoting EDI
- They enhance the inclusive culture and reputation of the University
- They enable the University to meet its Public Sector Duty Requirements

Equality Impact Assessment - The Process:

1. Having identified the need for a policy, the Policy Developer, as part of the UCD Policy Development Framework, contacts the EDI Unit (edi@ucd.ie) for support in conducting an Equality Impact Assessment.
2. The EDI Unit identifies a member of the EDI Group who will partner with the Policy Developer for the purposes of carrying out an EIA. An EIA is required to be carried out at policy proposal stage and after the policy is drafted, in advance of submission to the relevant body for approval.
3. The EDI Group member meets with the Policy Developer and supports them in carrying out an EIA at the various stages, offering advice and occasionally bringing in additional expertise.
4. Once the policy including the completed EIA, is submitted for approval to the approval body, the EDI Group member ensures that a copy of the Equality Impact Assessment and any feedback is submitted to the EDI Unit.
5. During periodic reviews of your policy, the EIA form should also be reviewed to ensure it remains consistent with UCD's 10 grounds.

The EIA is currently being reviewed following the pilot to streamline and refine the EIA process and also to expand beyond policy such as the development of processes. Workshop will take place with those who provided support to policy developers from an EDI perspective and also the policy developers themselves to see how the tool could be enhanced. Once the process is reviewed it will then be expanded to processes etc.

All policies for review and development since the EIA was developed have undergone an EIA. This has had the impact of ensuring that EDI has been mainstreamed into policy development and policy developers have taken ownership of EDI. Whilst members of the EDI group support policy developers in undertaking the EIA, it is the responsibility of the policy developer to ensure that the EIA is carried out and any mitigating actions are taken if an issue is identified. It also ensures that the policy developer considers how the policy can promote EDI in the University. This supports the University's aims where we reach a stage that EDI is part of everybody's work and a key consideration rather than an add-on activity.

UNIVERSITY COLLEGE DUBLIN: GENDER IDENTITY AND EXPRESSION

PROJECT TITLE	Gender Identity and Expression
RESPONSIBLE	University College Dublin
CONTACT PERSON	Marcellina Fogarty
PHONE NUMBER	+35317164947
E-MAIL ADDRESS	Marcellina.fogarty@ucd.ie
TIME FRAME	September 2016 – May 2017
FUNDING	Internal
BUDGET (IN €)	Training budget € 5,000
TARGET GROUP	Students and Staff
WEBPAGE	http://www.ucd.ie/equality/information/policies/genderidentityexpression/

This project was undertaken to create an inclusive culture for the University community irrespective of gender identity, and to respect and recognise diverse gender identities and expressions. This involved the development of a Gender Identity and Expression policy and guidelines, together with a broad range of activities, to embed the inclusive culture we wanted in UCD. Main objective - create an inclusive culture for all gender identities so the University community can reach their full potential. Achieved by:

- Development of Gender Identity and Expression policy and guidelines in line with the University strategy and values.
- Campaign to raise awareness around gender identity.
- Recognition of different gender identities through variety of measures.
- Equipping key members of UCD with skills and knowledge to implement the policy.

This policy supports the achievement of UCD's strategy, particularly: "To attract and retain an excellent and diverse cohort of students, faculty and staff". It demonstrates we are an inclusive University that welcomes all genders and recognise all equality groups are valuable sources of talent. To retain talent, we must deliver on commitments to people of all genders.

UCD has six core values driving culture; Excellence; Integrity; Collegiality; Engagement; Diversity and Creativity. In line with these, UCD is committed to providing an inclusive and diverse environment where all members of UCD is respected and valued for unique perspectives and contributions, and achieve potential. Becoming an employer and University of choice is a HR Strategic Objective, with a key initiative to champion and mainstream Equality, Diversity and Inclusion (EDI). An EDI Working Group was established consisting of key stakeholder representatives across UCD: EDI LGBTI sub-group, EDI Unit, Vice-President for EDI, LGBTI Network, Students, Registry and Sports and Leisure. This group was chaired by the Director of Culture and Engagement, UCD HR. Transgender Equality Network Ireland (TENI) was invited to present to the group to ensure all members had a good level of understanding of gender identity. Members were trained in facilitation skills by a consultant in order to carry out consultation. The group engaged with the University Management Team (UMT) on many occasions to ensure they were brought on the journey. Specific Actions taken included:

Engaged with UMT to get buy-in for policy development (August 2016)

Established Working Group and invited TENI to first meeting (September 2016)

Drafted policy and procedures based on best practice, advice from expert bodies and UCD objectives.

Undertook face-to-face University-wide consultation with employees and students (April 2017).
Uploaded policy and procedure to website with option for anonymous feedback.

Policy and guidelines approved by UMT (June 2017). Key actions:

- Gender neutral signage on single stall facilities across UCD to ensure all buildings have at least one gender neutral facility. Signs placed outside existing multi-stall facilities: “Please choose the facilities that best fits your gender” and internally “Please remember that we are an inclusive and diverse University where all members of our community must be respected”. These signs are piloted in UCD Sports and Leisure Centre to be gradually extended across UCD. All refurbishments/new builds will include gender neutral facilities.
- Training – external consultant carried out workshops with frontline staff (over 120 people) to raise awareness and equip them with the knowledge and skills to implement the policy.
- Name change – a staff member or student transitioning can have their name changed on UCD systems without official documentation i.e. Gender Recognition Cert (GRC). Measures have been taken to ensure the “original” name will not appear on any system, correspondence etc.
- Official transcripts can now be issued in the person’s preferred name without a GRC.
- Documentation is being amended to ensure that gender options are available: Male/Female/Gender Non-binary/Self Declare_____/Prefer not to say. Systems will be updated to reflect this.
- Culture and Engagement survey in 2018 incorporated 9 equality grounds into the survey so responses can be analysed accordingly, including gender identity.
- Recent policy development re-enforces the message around inclusiveness and respect for all grounds. The EDI policy was approved in May 2018 and Dignity and Respect policy in 2017.
- The University developed an Equality Impact Assessment as a mandatory element of policy development, requiring policy developers to ensure policies are not discriminatory and promote EDI.
- Awareness raising is an important means of embedding of this policy. It was launched in February 2018 by Minister of Children and Youth Affairs, Katherine Zappone and reported on national TV and newspapers. Gender Identity and Expression is incorporated into Orientation for staff, students and new Heads of School.
- UCD is the first Irish University to join OUTstanding which helps companies harness LGBT+. UCD also has LGBTI staff and student networks in place and an EDI LGBTI sub-group.

This was an innovative approach in terms of:

- Inclusive approach in terms of broad membership of the group and University-wide consultation process.
- Name change for students/employees without a GRC.
- Official degree awarded in persons preferred name.
- Workshops with frontline staff.
- Signage across UCD to ensure people can avail of facilities of the gender they identify with and that all genders must be respected.
- Culture and Engagement survey – question on gender identity.

Learnings:

- Influencing colleagues at all levels
- Developing a business case and pushing boundaries.
- Establishing a working group representative of all genders and key stakeholders
- Consultation with entire University community
- Engaged external experts who shared professional and/or personal experience.
- Challenged norms, assumptions and biases while working in a collegial manner.
- Embedded values of EDI throughout process and afterwards.

The culture and engagement survey will enable us to analyse responses based on gender identity. The fact that people will identify their gender in this survey demonstrates that people feel safe to disclose their gender.

GHENT UNIVERSITY: COACHING AND DIVERSITY

PROJECT TITLE	Coaching and Diversity
RESPONSIBLE	Ghent University – Diversity and Gender Policy Unit
CONTACT PERSON	Marieken De Munter
PHONE NUMBER	+3292649827
E-MAIL ADDRESS	coachingendiversiteit@ugent.be
TIME FRAME	October 2013 – unlimited
FUNDING	Internal
BUDGET (IN €)	€ 3,000
TARGET GROUP	Disadvantaged students
WEBPAGE	www.ugent.be/coachingendiversiteit

Ghent University wants its students to become world citizens, who take up an active, critical and independent role in a changing society. The educational concept of Community Service Learning – an educational approach that integrates service in the community with intentional learning activities - was launched to turn this strategic goal into concrete actions. As a pedagogical approach, Community Service Learning offers the opportunity to integrate the original voluntary based mentoring initiative into a curriculum based learning experience. In 2013, the UGhent mentoring program became an elective course unit (3 ECTS) for master students. The course, named ‘Coaching and Diversity’, includes (1) the practice of mentoring, (2) theoretical knowledge on diversity issues/ coaching techniques and (3) critical reflection. First, master students practice their knowledge and skills by engaging as mentors for a first year student in need of support and guidance in their studying and socializing process. Second, ‘Coaching and Diversity’ offers master students theoretical knowledge on diversity (such as correcting prejudices, disability awareness), conversation techniques, motivational speeches and didactics. Lastly, mentors learn to reflect critically on their experiences, learning processes and civic engagement through a personal portfolio and planned peer-reviews.

Minority students are underrepresented in higher education. Proportionately few of them find their way to higher education and when they do, there is a significantly higher dropout rate. At first, mentoring was only offered to ethnic minority students, mainly refugees. Due to its success results, the Mentoring Project expanded the following years, to all categories of disadvantaged student groups such as students with disabilities, students with atypical preliminary training, pioneer students and underprivileged talent. In October 2018 we recruited 105 mentors. Qualitative research (by Steunpunt Diversiteit en Leren in 2015; Van Hiel in 2016; Directie onderwijsaangelegenheden in 2017) shows that mentoring improves academic and social integration of students-at-risk. Mentoring works. The threshold for guidance has been reduced. The academic language proficiency had improved. The mentees can rely on a more intensive network, they have a greater self-confidence and an increased feeling of independence. Besides the improvement of academic and social success of first year minority students, this course gives UGhent community the opportunity to simultaneously reach one of its strategic goals: strengthening diversity and coaching competencies of mentor-students will lead to alumni who are indeed world citizens and who take up an vigorous, analytical, passionate and autonomous role in a changing society.

GHENT UNIVERSITY: HEFORSHE@UGENT

PROJECT TITLE	HeForShe@UGent
RESPONSIBLE	Ghent University
CONTACT PERSON	Tine Brouckaert
PHONE NUMBER	+3292649838
E-MAIL ADDRESS	tine.brouckaert@ugent.be
TIME FRAME	11.11.2016
FUNDING	Internal
BUDGET (IN €)	€ 50,000
TARGET GROUP	Potential students/students/staff members/top leaders of university

In November 2016, Ghent University launched its own HeForShe Campaign, which made Ghent University the first and only university in Belgium promoting this initiative. Because leaders carry this initiative, the deans from all faculties, who are all men, actively participate in the UGent HeForShe Campaign. In a video recording, every dean (11 in total) personally expressed their engagement to strive for more gender equality and talked about which subjects and areas they would like to improve in their faculty. During 4 years, every faculty is enrolling their engagement + going further by learning from each other and being inspired by each other.

Big impact. In two years' time, we went from 8 to 26% women in top leading positions. From 0 female deans in the last 18 years (and only 5 in the last 200 years) we went to 6 female candidates (from which 3 elected) in 2018. We developed our own gender bias training for staff members and leaders, and enrolled it within university. Same evolution with 'the active bystander training'. We had also the VirGo-project springing out of this campaign, focusing on high potential girls with migration background followed-up from the age of 10 until 18 years old. It is an inclusive project, meaning that boys are also participating.

UNIVERSIDAD POLITÉCNICA DE MADRID: EQUALITY UNIT

PROJECT TITLE	Equality Unit
RESPONSIBLE	Universidad Politécnica de Madrid
CONTACT PERSON	Paloma García-Maroto
PHONE NUMBER	+34910670652
E-MAIL ADDRESS	unidad.igualdad@upm.es
TIME FRAME	Since September 2009 - present
FUNDING	<p>External funding</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Scholarships "Thales for Diversity" Thales Spain, - "I Want to be an Engineer Program" Grant from the Women's Institute. <p>Non-funded external collaborations</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - "STEM Talent Girl" project with ASTI Foundation and Comunidad de Madrid - Project "Ahora Tú" Institute for Women. - UP4Gender within the UP4 Alliance, - Member of Gender Policy Group within Sectorial Sustainability of CRUE - Network of Gender Equality Units for University Excellence (RUIGEU), - Network of Gender Equality Units of Madrid Universities (RUIGEMA) to be part of CRUMA
BUDGET (IN €)	Circa € 100,000 annually
TARGET GROUP	Entire University community and teenage female high school students.
WEBPAGE	http://www.upm.es/UPM/Politicasiigualdad

The main objective of this Unit is to promote policies of gender equality within UPM, whose competencies are:

- Prepare, implement, monitor and evaluate equality plans at the University.
- Inform and advise the governing bodies of the University regarding equality policies.
- Carry out studies in order to promote gender equality.
- Promote knowledge in the university community on the scope and meaning of the principle of equality through the formulation of proposals for training actions.

The following documents and reports have been published:

- Gender Equality Plan in the UPM
- Manifiesto 25 November 2018. International Day for the Elimination of Violence against Women
- Program "Ahora Tú"
- First edition of the TALGO Foundation Prize for Professional Excellence in Women Engineering
- Video of the Women, Sports and Health Conference 7-11-2018
- Equality Unit Brochure
- STEM Talent Girl Project
- Protocol of Sexual Harassment and Harassment by reason of sex
- Harassment Prevention Guide
- Madrid Strategy against Gender Violence 2016-2021
- Madrid strategy for equal opportunities between women and men 2018-2021

Impacts and policy reforms, achieved so far:

- UPM regulation: Maternal (paternal) leave taken periods do not harm the possibilities of the Faculty to obtain a positive teaching evaluation
- UPM regulation: Maternal leave for hired professors does not harm their promotion to become tenured faculty
- Strategy Men for Women (men supporting women in committees, events...)
- Training course (with 20 UPM personnel) about Basic notions of Gender Equality
- Individual Counselling offered by the Leading person of the Equality Unit about the Protocol against Sexual Harassment (15 individuals per year).
- Work to pass a protocol to provide support and assistance to LGTBT
- Art exhibitions and Roundtables